

COMPUTER SCIENCES

DATA PROCESSING ALGORITHMS IN INFOCOMMUNICATION SYSTEMS

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Abstract

The paper analyzes the features of effective methods for processing and transmitting data over infocommunication networks and the possibilities of improving the quality of data by using modern algorithms and restrictions on the basic duration of the code element used as the basis for constructing timer signal structures. The possibilities of increasing the channel performance by reducing the energy distance between timer signal structures, where the information parameter is time, are investigated. The disadvantages of classical coding methods with redundant codes are determined and the algorithms for generating signal structures of traditional noise-immune positional codes are analyzed. At the same time, positional coding is inferior in such important data transmission parameters as information capacity and entropy. In addition, the results of calculating the quality indicators of data transmission are significantly affected by the language used in the transmitted text information or the volume of the analyzed text, and it is proposed to use a certain/adapted type of coding for the transmitted data. A comparative analysis and assessment of the influence of the studied parameters on the quality of data transmission are carried out. Practical confirmation of the correctness of the results obtained is achieved by simulating a virtual transmission system with different coding principles on a software model.

Keywords: data processing algorithms, Nyquist element, information segment, signal code construction, Hamming code, positional code, information element, noise immunity.

I. INTRODUCTION

The main problem of further development of infocommunication systems is creation and provision of differential services (QoS - Quality of Service) with the corresponding quality of service (SLA - Service Level Agreement). At the same time, the main tasks of the differential service quality assurance system are to increase the speed of information transfer and maintain high reliability of information reception. The solution of such problems is achieved by increasing the efficiency of the transmission system and using error-correcting coding [1]. To increase the efficiency of the transmission system, it is proposed to use multi-level timer signals, which allow to significantly increase the speed of information transfer [2-3], and the increase in the fidelity of information reception is achieved by using error-correcting coding in information transmission systems [4-6]. Thus, the use of these two methods allows to build effective infocommunication systems.

The disadvantages of traditional approaches to building telephone networks are low efficiency and the ability to transport all types of information using passive optical networks. At the same time, providing access to transport networks is a key issue for most telecommunications operators. One of the main problems is the task of effectively using the transmission medium capacity and increasing spectral efficiency in the process of developing modern telecommunications networks. This problem is solved using overlay networks

based on multiple access with code and time division of channels, which uses CDMA and TDMA technologies and makes it possible to theoretically use the allocated frequency band twice as efficiently [3].

In the known works, the main attention is paid to positional coding based on noise-resistant (redundant) codes and the use of multi-level timer signal structures allows to increase the information transfer rate in comparison with positional coding. However, no comparisons have been made between positional and timer coding based on the entropy assessment of code words and the information capacity of the Nyquist element [6]. Certain works [3-8] are devoted to the development of efficient algorithms for the formation of noise-resistant codes and methods for their decoding. An analysis of these works, as well as research in the field of data transmission and reception, have shown that high noise immunity of signal reception is achieved with a large length of code combinations. Based on the conducted research, algorithms for constructing efficient timer code structures [6-8] were proposed, which were used in the development of timer code structures of long codes having a certain code rate, as well as the maximum possible code distance between the nearest code combinations and, with an increase in the length of the code structure, the proportion of correctable errors. According to classical theory, such codes allow achieving high fidelity of message reception by increasing the code length without increasing the transmitter output

power. The structure of the error-correcting code must be regular for the implementation of the algorithms for encoding messages and decoding the received code structures. The regularity of the code structure implies that the algorithm for generating code structures corresponding to the information sequences of symbols arriving at the encoder input corresponds to certain mathematical rules and must be simple enough.

It is known [6-8] that for modern transmission systems, information is contained in the information parameter on a fixed interval of the Nyquist element. The throughput is increased by increasing the number of states of the information parameter on this interval: the number of different amplitudes, phases, and oscillation frequencies. In turn, the peculiarity of positional encoding is that the number of symbols transmitted over the channel, presented in binary form in the form of information segments with durations multiple of the Nyquist element, corresponds to the number of consecutively transmitted ones or zeros in the number [6-8].

II. Principles of construction and implementation of algorithms of positional codes for processing digital data

2.1. Basic principles of construction of positional codes

Positional coding is understood as [8] the representation of the number N through the weight coefficients of the number system corresponding to the alphabet of the channel " a ":

$$N = d_n a^n + \dots + d_2 a^2 + d_1 a^1 + d_0 a^0, \quad (1)$$

$$d = 0; 1; \dots (a - 1).$$

where a – is the number of states of the information parameter.

It can be noted that with an increase in the code distance " d " the number of digits in the representation of the same number (1) decreases.

The amount of information in positional code words (H) is determined by the number of information elements in them. If the code is simple [8], i.e. all N_m code words are used, then

$$H = \log_2 N_m = \log_2 a^n = n \log_2 a. \quad (2)$$

From expression (1) it follows that if $a > 2$, then with positional coding each element contains more than one bit of information. Existing communication systems use redundant codes in which each combination contains m information elements and r additional (redundant) elements [7]:

$$n = m + r.$$

For example, in a code with an even number of units, only $(n - 1)$ elements are informational, and in a 9-element Hamming code there are 5 information elements and 4 check elements [5], therefore, the entropy of each code word $H_0 = 5$, and the information capacity of one element $I_H = 5/9 = 0.555 \dots$

It should be noted that each code word in positional coding is transmitted by the channel with coefficients x_i , the signal duration of each of which is equal to the duration of the Nyquist element [4]

$$t_0 = (1/\Delta F) \cdot t,$$

where ΔF – is the frequency band of the signal spectrum.

In works [8-11], the conditions for data transmission over channels with a base are analyzed:

$$B = t_0 \times \Delta F = 1 \div 2,$$

where t_0 – is the duration of the transient process at the output of the channel with the band ΔF ;

$\Delta F \rightarrow := \frac{1}{\Delta F}$ – which is called the Nyquist element itself. The band ΔF is understood as the real band ΔF_p divided by 1.3 (a decrease of 30% is associated with the nonlinearity of the amplitude and phase-frequency characteristics).

Individual elements a_i of the decomposition (1) are transmitted to the data transmission channel as signal segments of duration t_0 with different amplitudes, frequencies or initial phases. At the moment of changing the coefficient in the representation (1), modulation (change) of the information parameter occurs.

It is known [7,8] that the main disadvantages of the positional coding method are the minimum energy distance between code words and the impossibility of adjusting this parameter, therefore, increasing the number of implementations in a given time interval.

2.2. Implementation of positional coding algorithms for digital data processing

Let us consider the practical application of algorithms of the positional method of digital data processing for the transmission of two symbolic ensembles of text information of a given alphabet during encoding. The calculations were performed using the software environment for solving engineering problems Scilab [10]. As is known, the amount of information in positional encoding is determined by expression (2). So, for example, to transmit 32 symbols of the alphabet according to (2), 5 code elements are required ($\log_2 32 = 5$), and to transmit two symbolic ensembles ($N_p = 32 \cdot 32 = 1024$), $\log_2 1024 = 10$ elements in the code word are required (similarly, to transmit 3-symbol ensembles, the length of the code words will be equal to $3 \log_2 32 = 15$ elements). Thus, we can conclude that when transmitting information of $0 - Z$ symbols of the alphabet by one code word, there is a linear dependence of the number of elements of the group combination on the multiplicity of Z symbolic ensembles. It should be noted that with different methods that provide the formation of (32^Z) different combinations, the total number of elements n in the code word is equal to

$$n_\Sigma = Z \cdot \log_2 32.$$

Let the number of realizations be $N_{p1} = 23$ and $N_{p2} = 31$. To form 1024 code words, one can use one code word with the number of elements $n_1 = 10$ or two code words with 5 elements $n_1 = n_2 = 5$, or two code words with $n_1 = 2$ and $n_2 = 8$ with subsets of the numbers of realizations $N_{p1} = 2^2$ and $N_{p8} = 2^8$, which will provide the total number of realizations ($4 \cdot 256 = 1024$). With $n_1 = 3$ and $n_2 = 7$, the subsets will be $2^3 = 8$; $2^7 = 128$; ($n_{\Sigma} = 3 + 7 = 10$) with the same number of realizations ($8 \cdot 128 = 1024$) [11]. As was indicated, in positional coding the distance between adjacent modulation moments is a multiple of the duration of the Nyquist element itself, which limits the power of the realized set on the interval of n elements. The elements of the code word n are determined by the number of different states of the coded source N_K [4]:

$$n = E^+ \log_2 N_K,$$

where E^+ – is the symbol of an integer greater than $\log_2 N_K$ and then from (1) and (2) it follows that the maximum number N for binary signals does not exceed 2^n .

In correcting (redundant, not necessarily linear) codes, the maximum number of additional r elements is determined by the boundary, i.e. the Varshamov-Gilbert limit value [2]:

$$2^{n-m} = 2^r \geq \sum_{i=0}^{d_0-2} c_n^i - 1,$$

where d_0 – is the required code distance.

Table I shows the numbers of redundant elements r , for $m \in 1 \div 15$, $d_1 = 3$ and $d_2 = 5$.

Table I

Number of check elements for $d \in \text{const}$ data

d_0/m	2	3	4	5	6	12	13	14	15
3	3	3	3	3	4	5	5	5	5
5	7	8	8	9	9	14	15	15	15

As follows from Table I, with a code distance of $d = 5$ and $m \geq 1$ implementation intervals, the number of redundant elements during positional coding of a large amount of information increases significantly, which makes such a code ineffective.

III. Principles of construction and implementation of algorithms of timer signal structures for processing digital data

3.1. Basic principles of constructing timer signal structures

When forming timer code structures [12], in contrast to the positional encoding method, when information about the transmitted discharge is determined by the type of signal on a single (Nyquist) interval, the infor-

mation is embedded in the number of information segments "i" located on the interval $T_{sk} = mt_0$, their locations on the interval T_{sk} and the duration of each ($\tau_{si} \geq t_0 + z\Delta$, ($k \in 1; 2; \dots z$ is an integer)). The value of Δ determines the step of changing the durations of the segments, ensuring a given probability of erroneous determination of the duration of the segments " τ_{si} " on reception (for a standard channel $\Delta = \frac{t_0}{7} = 0.143 \cdot t_0$ (Table II)).

As an example, Table II shows the quality of transmission of code words by a standard data transmission channel using positional coding (PC) and coding due to the duration of individual signals " τ_{si} " of code structures (timer signal structures - TSS).

Table II

Comparative parameters of position and timer coding

Positional coding (PC)				Timer signal structures (TSS), for $s = 7$ ($\Delta = 0.143t_0$)			
N	N_{tr}	N_{er}	P_{er}	n	N_{tr}	N_{er}	P_{er}
10	10^6	700	7×10^{-4}	9	10^6	104	$1,04 \times 10^{-4}$
20	10^6	770	$7,7 \times 10^{-4}$	17	10^6	1150	$11,5 \times 10^{-4}$
40	10^6	1500	15×10^{-3}	33	10^6	1620	$1,6 \times 10^{-3}$

The following notations are used in Table II: N_{tr} – is the number of transmitted code words; N_{er} – is the number of errors in received code words; P_{er} – is the length of the code word of the Nyquist element itself.

It follows from the Table II that the energy distance between the communication channels (CC) for TSS is determined by the energy, which is 7 times less than for PC ($s = 7$), (the error probabilities for close durations of the CC differ insignificantly).

The duration of each of the signal segments of the signal structure is not less than the Nyquist interval [12-13]:

$$\tau_{si} = t_0 + z\Delta,$$

where $z\Delta \in 0 \div z_0$ are integers.

A part of a single element of a single element $t_0 > \Delta = \frac{t_0}{s}$ is determined by the parameters of interference in the channel and the permissible probability of erroneous reception of the signal structure ($s \in 2, 4, \dots, s_0$).

The application of t_0 in (3) ensures the establishment of a transient process at the channel output when transmitting all "i" segments of each signal structure, and $z\Delta$ carries information about the code word.

3.2. Implementation of algorithms of timer signal structures for digital data processing

It is known [12-15] that the power (the number of realizations of the TSS, (N_p)) on the interval m of the most Nyquist elements can be determined by the expression:

$$N_p = C_{ms-i(s-1)}^i.$$

After expanding expression (4) we obtain:

$$N_p = \frac{(ms-i(s-1))!}{i!(ms-is)!}.$$

The number of realizations N_p (powers) of timer signal structures calculated by algorithm (5), under certain specified conditions are presented in Table III.

Table III

The number of realizations of the tsk and the amount of information in the Nyquist

S/m	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
	$2^4 = 16$	$2^5 = 32$	$2^6 = 64$	$2^7 = 128$	$2^8 = 256$	$2^9 = 512$	$2^{10} = 1024$
2	10/0,83	35/1,026	84/1,065	165/1,052	286/1,02	455/0,98	680/0,941
4	35/1,282	165/1,473	455/1,472	969/1,417	1771/1,349	2925/1,279	4495/1,213
6	84/1,598	455/1,766	1330/1,730	2925/1,645	5456/1,552	9139/1,462	14190/1,379
8	165/1,842	969/1,984	2925/1,919	6545/1,811	12341/1,699	20825/1,594	32509/1,499
10	286/2,039	1771/2,158	5456/2,068	12341/1,941	23426/1,814	39711/1,697	62196/1,592

In Table III, the numerator shows the number of realizations of the TSS for $i = 3, m \in 4 \div 10$, for $s = 2; 4; 6; 8; 10$, and the denominator is the amount of information contained in one element:

$$I_H = \frac{\log_2 N_p}{m}.$$

It follows from Table III:

- in a binary channel, without changing the alphabet, due to a sharp increase in the number of repetitions $N_p \gg 2^m$, more than two bits of information $I_H = \log_2 2 = 1$) can be transmitted on one Nyquist element (with positional coding);
- with an increase in m at $s = \text{const}$, the information capacity of the Nyquist element itself increases to m_{max} (after m_{max} it decreases);
- the maximum amount of information per element is transmitted with a signal structure length $T_{sk} = 5t_0$;
- when changing the channel alphabet, the number of realizations when changing the channel alphabet i , therefore, I_H will increase significantly;
- for example, if $a = 5$, the number of realizations will increase by $[(5/2)]^3 = 15.625$ times. Then for $m = 8, i = 3$ and $s = 7$ (Table III) the number of releases will be $(8436 \cdot 15.625) = 133375$, that is, one Nyquist element will contain ($I_H = \log_2 133375$) more than 17 bits of information.

IV. Principles of construction and implementation of Hamming code algorithms for processing digital data.

Basic principles of Hamming code formation.

Hamming code that allows to correct errors of multiplicity and should have a minimum code distance $d_M = 2t_{HO}$. The number of elements of the code combination is determined by the inequality [5]:

$$2^m = \frac{2n}{1+n}. \tag{7}$$

This code is constructed in such a way that the number of redundant elements and the number of checks $(n - m)$ correspond to r the check sums of "5" information elements [4-5].

Each of the sums as an addend includes the following information elements:

$$\begin{aligned} S_1 &= a_1 + a_3 + a_5 + a_7 + a_9; \\ S_2 &= a_2 + a_3 + a_6 + a_7; \\ S_3 &= a_4 + a_5 + a_6 + a_7; \\ S_4 &= a_8 + a_9. \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

Equation (8) involves 9 elements, the numbers of which in binary and decimal codes correspond to Table IV:

Table IV

Binary equivalents of decimal numbers

Decimal code	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Binary code	0001	0010	0011	0100	0101	0110	0111	1000	1001	1010

It follows from the table that the sequence of using element numbers a_i in equations (8):

- the first sum includes numbers that have "1" in binary form in the first position from the left;
- the second sum includes elements that have "1" in the second position from the left, etc.

We present these patterns in the form of a table. In Table V, the numbers of code elements participating in certain sums in equation (8) are shown by the "+" sign:

Correspondence of elements to positions in equation (10)

№	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
1	+		+		+		+		+
2		+	+			+	+		
3				+	+	+	+		
4								+	+

Thus, the above analytical studies and calculations also apply to the case of using a nine-element Hamming code with the corresponding assumptions. Theoretical calculations have shown that the dynamics of change in the main quality parameters of transmission is preserved, the difference being in minor digital values.

V. Conclusion

The material presented in the article is based on a set of fundamental approaches to the formation of redundant codes and algorithms for the formation of timer signal structures based on traditional noise-immune positional codes and, therefore, can be used for successful analysis and synthesis of data transmission systems. Such signal structures allow synthesizing ensembles with a large information content compared to positional coding and, with a limitation on the length of the code word, the time of use of the infocommunication network device is reduced; by changing the number of information segments in the code words of timer codes with a constant value of the implementation interval, it is possible to increase the information transfer rate. When using the algorithm for forming timer signal structures, the resulting gain in the number of implementations can be used to create redundancy in order to ensure a given probability of erroneous reception. A higher implementation of timer signals in a given time interval, depending on the information feature of the most accurate element in the binary channel, can be used to create uniform transmissions of code symbols with an uneven first alphabet. In positional codes, with an increase in the number of information elements, the redundancy coefficient smoothly decreases and the noise immunity of the code decreases. In addition, the results of calculations of the qualitative indicators of data transmission are significantly influenced by the language used in the transmitted text information or the volume of the analyzed text, and it is proposed to use a specific/adapted type of encoding of the transmitted data.

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